

3

Building a multimodal VR arena

My VR system was built in a modular fashion to allow for different species and stimuli. In this chapter, I will explore the dynamic landscapes, windscares and odourscares that were then created to approximate stimuli that an insect might encounter in the natural world, employing tests that mimicked behaviours observed in the wild for my test species.

3.1 SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The MultiMoVR engine was written in Python and uses the open-source Panda3d game engine for rendering scenes. Diverse virtual Land-Wind-odoursapes and experimental paradigms can be programmed into the system and added to the Graphical User Interface (GUI) built using PyQt-Graph(www.pyqtgraph.org) (Figure 3.4 on page 44). The arena is a 32-cm-wide, 60-cm-tall prism-shaped arena composed of three 165-Hz in-plane switching (IPS) monitors (Asus Rog PG279Q; AsusTek Computer) (Figure 3.1 on page 41). A photorealistic scene based on real-world scenery is wrapped around the three monitors. (Figure 3.2 on page 42) The insect was placed in the geometric centre of the arena using a 3D printed manipulator¹³⁰.

The tethered insect is surrounded by capillaries that provide directional wind and odour (Figure 3.5 on page 45). Airflow and odour were delivered through one of the 16 capillaries surrounding the insect from a custom-built delivery system (Figure 3.8 on page 50). The entire assembly is supported using a 1-m-cubic frame composed of 20 × 20-mm generic aluminum profile extrusions.

The virtual environment is designed to provide 3D scenes with precise real-time manipulative abilities in all three modalities simultaneously. The virtual world is 1025 m x 1025 m with optional precisely tiled periodic boundaries. The paradigms used in the following experiments, such as gain optimization, choice assays, plume following, confounding input etc., are already included. Custom scenes can be loaded using .egg or .bam files, which can be designed using Blender (www.blender.org). The system was built on the Robot Operating System (ROS) architecture. ROS is used for communication, synchronization and hardware.

3.2 LANDSCAPE

The triangular-based prism was composed of three monitors (32 cm X 60 cm). My criterion were, higher refresh rates to reduce latency, an IPS display with a wide viewing angle, a matte finish to

Figure 3.1: The MultiMoVR, a MULTI MOdal Virtual Reality arena is a 32-cm-wide, 60-cm-tall prism-shaped arena composed of three 165-Hz in-plane switching (IPS) monitors. The tethered insect is surrounded by capillaries that provide directional wind and odour. A photorealistic scene based on real-world scenery is wrapped around the three monitors.

Figure 3.2: Ecologically relevant visual targets can be presented in my VR. Precise real-time perspective correction enables 360° visual input by mapping a 3D world on 2D monitors. A photorealistic scene based on real world scenery wrapped around the 3 monitors.

avoid glare, and thin bezels to minimize edge fixation. The monitor should be able to orient vertically, to cover a larger solid angle and increase the field of view.

For my experiments, an Asus ROG swift, with a 165 Hz IPS panel was chosen and subtended horizontal field of view of 360° and vertical field of view of 140°. The bezels were 5 mm wide and the luminosity at the insect's location was roughly 1000 lux. To make the scenery, the tree, for example, was modelled in Blender using 360° photos of fruit trees in an orchard with textures of real fruit, leaves and bark.

Seamless textures of grass and clouds were used for the ground and the sky to minimize seam fixation and to add clutter and optic flow. These textures and the virtual lighting were symmetrical to prevent side bias.

As the scenery was displayed on flat monitors forming a prism, the scene was corrected for perspective and distortion. The models and textures were scaled, distorted and projected such that they are scaled to real world proportions. So, for example, a 3 m tree that is 5 m away subtends the same visual angle for the individual in the VR as it does in the real world (Figure 3.3 on page 43, Equation 3.1 and 3.2).

Figure 3.3: Expected Real World (RW) angles vs measured VR angles of objects. The dashed green line is the reference 45° line for perfect mapping.

$$RealWorldAngle = 2 \cdot \arctan \left(\frac{ObjectRadius \cdot \cos \left(2 \cdot \arctan \left(\frac{ObjectRadius}{ObjectDistance} \right) \right)}{ObjectDistance - \left(ObjectRadius \cdot \sin \left(2 \cdot \arctan \left(\frac{ObjectRadius}{ObjectDistance} \right) \right) \right)} \right) \quad (3.1)$$

Figure 3.4: The custom-built GUI lets the user adjust experiment parameters and also monitor trajectories in real-time.

$$VirtualAngle = 2 \cdot \left(\frac{ObjectRadiusOnDisplay}{DistanceToDisplay} \right) \quad (3.2)$$

3.3 WINDSCAPE

The wind delivery system was a custom-built apparatus used to provide airflow and odour from any direction to the insect. There are five main parts to this mechanism. Four static parts with sixteen aligned holes for air to flow, viz., splitter, revolver holder, suction toroid and capillary holder. The revolver is the only moving part with a single hole for air to flow. Filtered, dry air was fed into the

splitter at 1 bar. Due to the geometry of the mechanism, only those holes that are aligned with that of the revolver form an unobstructed path for the air to the outlet at the animal. The remaining airflow is shunted through a large concentric bleed hole and removed by the suction toroid (Figure 3.6 on page 46). The capillary holder has sixteen L-bent capillaries all pointing radially inward (Figure 3.5 on page 45). The individual insect was positioned at the centre of these radial spokes and received airflow depending on which capillary was aligned. The revolver was controlled using a closed loop stepper motor (uStepper NEMA 17, uStepper Aps, Denmark) allowing precise positioning.

The revolver alignment hole is 2.5 holes wide (12.5 mm) and acts as a low pass filter in the transition of the wind direction by smoothing the handoff in the capillary alignments. This was the reason to not choose a valve-based system, as it creates large transients during a change in direction and is bulky. Present Mass Flow controllers can provide a smooth handoff but are too slow for my VR. To remediate these artefacts and to cut costs, I resorted to my current design. I used a 3D printer (Raise3D N2, Raise 3D Technologies, USA) to print most of the VR

equipment. I used 1.75mm PLA filament (WOL 3D silk, WOL 3D, India), (layer height:0.1mm, nozzle:0.4mm). The 3D designs are resilient and can be replicated with different settings and materials. The Windfield can be loaded as an image mapped to wind direction at that virtual coordinate. The relative angle between the insect's current heading and the wind direction at a virtual location of the insect was used to position the revolver hole. For example, if the insect was heading north and

Figure 3.5: Closed loop airflow input. Using bent glass capillaries in 360°, the fly can be made to feel airflow from any direction.

the wind was blowing from the east, the revolver hole was positioned such that the air was blown from the capillary on the right side of the insect. This alignment procedure was performed for every frame in the closed wind condition. In open wind cases, regardless of the insect's heading, the wind always blew from the same front capillary as per the configuration. Image sequences were used for dynamic windfields. Experiment logic using the current state was used for context based windfield. In the slip scenario, the effective translational velocity of the insect was the vector sum of the individual's translational velocity (typically, 0.5 m/s) and wind velocity (typically, 0.2 m/s). Thus, when the insect was heading upwind, its effective translational velocity was 0.3 m/s, while it was 0.8 m/s during downwind heading. But during crosswind and everything between, along with a different velocity, the individual also experienced a visual side slip since the left and right visual fields have different optic flow velocities. All of these parameters can be easily modified in the GUI.

Dynamic directional airflow and odour were developed and incorporated using a custom-built delivery system. (Figure 3.8 on page 50) The standalone parametric design allows customization to provide "windfields" and odour cues, and an open-source package with a Graphical User Interface (GUI) allows for the adjustment of experimental paradigms. (Figure 3.4 on page 44) The wind

delivery system design was a result of multiple iterations which tackled issues ranging from unintentional visual input by moving parts, decoupled wind and odour systems, rapid loss of odourant, a dramatic loss in air pressure and headspace contamination.

The initial design had a simple design of an odour exit port and a suction pipe on a servo arm

Figure 3.6: Closed loop airflow input. Using a toroid with targeted odour suction holes enables rapid fall time in odour input.

similar to prior studies. But the motion of the servo itself created unintentional behavioural responses of moving object avoidance by the insects. After multiple attempts at minimizing the visual signature, I resorted to the current choice of concealing the moving parts. The next challenge was wind and odour being decoupled. I added 16 capillaries for the wind along with the previous odour exit port. This design allowed the user to control only the direction of the wind but not the direction of odour. This unintentional confounding input produced inconsistent behavioural responses. To remediate this, I connected the odourous line directly into the wind delivery system. This allowed control of both wind and odour direction simultaneously. Initially, there was a severe loss of air through the bleed holes. But this also meant rapid depletion of odour in the headspace of the odour bottles. Increasing concentrations and volumes did not alleviate this issue as the depletion rate far exceeded the volatility of the blend. To remediate this, I created a U-turn of the odour entering the revolver and exiting only at the aligned hole which reduced odour losses dramatically. Along with this, I added a toroid with precisely placed holes to suck out bleed hole content and local insect headspace and prevent contamination while still having form factor to fit inside the VR and occlude as little of the visual field as possible.

Measuring airflow velocities that exit from tiny capillaries is challenging. Due to the scale, vane based anemometer is simply too heavy and have high inertia to even start rotating. However, hot wire anemometers do not suffer from this issue. Under the “typical” usecases, they are inserted in windtunnels and ventilation ducts, which have large volume of directional airflow and their reading is invariant with position or orientation. In our scenario of measuring the jet airflow exiting a 1 mm capillary, few degrees change in orientation or few mm change in position and the measurement is completely different. To tackle this challenge, I swept through all angles and position to measure the maximum velocity signal.

Figure 3.7: The odour stimulus duration was varied and odour amount was quantified using a Photo Ionization Detector (PID). 18ms was the smallest, reliable puff duration.

3.4 ODOURSCAPE

Filtered, dry air at 3 bar was fed into a 3/2 valve. The valve outputs were sent to odour bottles made of PEEK. The odour bottles contained about 400 μl of 10^{-4} fruit volatile blends made in mineral oil (apple or hawthorn) to provide similar stimulation as prior wind tunnel studies¹³¹ and refilled after about two hours of usage. The control bottles contained only mineral oil. The valve was controlled using a MOSFET relay which received TTL pulses from an Arduino. The Arduino sends pulses based on the serial commands sent from the GUI. The output of the odour or control bottles was sent to a hole in the capillary holder. This central hole is aligned with another hole in the revolver creating a non-tangling airflow joint. The air from the revolver passes through a tunnel and exits into the revolver's alignment hole. The upward air current coming from the splitter carries this low-velocity valve output. The closed loop stepper motor and the valve receive commands from the GUI and this allows the user to simultaneously simulate mechanical stimulus from any direction and control the timing and duration of odour input with high precision.

The odour field has two layers, odourFrequency and odourLocation. The odourFrequency is a grayscale image, where the brightness corresponds to the packet frequency of the odour. The odourLocation is a binary image that indicates which coordinates in space have the odour and which don't. The pixel value of the odourLocation at the current virtual position of the individual denotes odour presence/absence. If present, the pixel value of the odourFrequency image at the current virtual position denotes the packet frequency of odour. For example, if odourLocation was true and odourFrequency was 3 Hz, then odour was pulsed at 3 puffs/second. Using the odourLocation and odourFrequency images, arbitrary odour plumes can be generated. These images can be drawn by hand using any image editing software and loaded into VR using the GUI. Although not incorporated in these analyses, odour concentration could also be dynamically altered through the digital flowmeters (Alicat MC-100SCCM-D, USA) at up to 5 Hz.

The design and components of the odour delivery system was based on previous literature⁹⁹, which had already characterized the components and system dynamics using a variety of odour and timing combinations. To verify the odour delivery system integrity, I swept through a range of puff durations and measured odour amount using a Photo Ionization Detector (PID, 200B miniPID, Aurora Scientific, Canada) with isoamyl acetate diluted in mineral oil at $10^{-3} \mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ as the odour source. The choice of the test odour was based on its low ionization energy and its presence in the odour blend of hawthorn flies, making it easy to detect and also be comparable to the blends used in experiments. The puff duration was finally set to 200 ms but can be adjusted by the user, to a minimum of 18 ms as per measured system limitations (Figure 3.7 on page 48).

3.5 CLOSED LOOP

In closed-loop systems, a fraction of the output is fed back to the input and this scaling factor is commonly known as “gain.” To estimate the optimal gain range for measuring long-range search, I

Figure 3.8: Closed-loop wind and odour delivery system design with a revolver controlling the direction of wind and odour controlled by a 3/2 valve.

devised a gain sweep protocol to measure the stability and manoeuvrability of the insect. (Figure 3.13 on page 58). Wing Beat Amplitude Difference (WBAD) (Figure 3.9 on page 52) is used to close the loop (Equation 3.3 and 3.4) and was measured in real-time from the camera feed using Kinefly. To prevent any side bias due to tethering artefacts, a DC offset parameter was adjusted by the user for every tested insect. This made sure that the WBAD distribution was symmetrical. The insect was given a fixed translational velocity (0.5-1 m/s), and based on the insect's virtual position and heading, the Land-Wind-odourscape were updated correspondingly in real-time.

$$WBAD = LeftWingAmplitude - RightWingAmplitude \quad (3.3)$$

$$NewHeading = CurrentHeading - Gain * WBAD \quad (3.4)$$

To close the loop (see definitions in Table A.1), I modified a gaming camera to measure wing beat amplitude difference in tethered flying insects and correspondingly adjust the yaw rotation of the scene. As measured directly from input to final closed loop translation visualized on the monitors, the latency of visual, wind and odour components was 66, 36 and 60 ± 4 ms respectively.

A modified PS3 eye camera (Sony Corporation, Japan) was used to film the insect. The camera was chosen for its ultra-low cost, High refresh rate (187 fps) and ease of modification. The IR cut filter was removed to allow observation in IR. A modified C-mount 5 -50 mm lens (CP-AC550 Pashay, India) with DC iris removed was used in place of the stock lens. However, due to the difference in lens sizes and a constraint to focus very close objects, a custom 3D printed M12 to C-mount extension tube adaptor was attached. The small sensor size along with a large format lens provided magnification, wide focal range and a large working distance at low cost. The camera was mounted on a DSLR macro focus rail (10033981, Neewer, China), which itself is mounted on a ball head mount (generic). This jointly provides pan, tilt, zoom, x, y and z (focus ring) degrees of freedom for

Figure 3.9: Wing Beat Amplitude Difference (WBAD) and Wing Beat Amplitude Sum (WBAS) is measured as the difference (L-R) and sum (L+R) of the angles of the left (L) wing and right (R) wing respectively. The wing hinge is used as the pivot point and the head-abdomen line is used as the vertical reference.

Figure 3.10: The insect was placed in the geometric centre of the arena using a 3D printed manipulator. Goosenecks from generic USB LED lamps were used for precise fine adjustment of lighting. The dim, visible LED was replaced with a high power, narrow beam IR emitter.

Figure 3.11: The camera is placed on a ball head mount that allows the pitch, yaw and roll adjustments. The ball head is mounted on an XY stage used in macro imaging enabling 2D translation adjustments. This entire setup is on a tripod Z rail which enables height adjustment. The camera itself has a large varifocal 5-50mm telephoto lens for adjusting the field of view. This versatility allows a single setup to film a tiny 5mm drosophila to a 50mm large hawkmoth.

the camera. This allows insects of various sizes (SI Appendix, MovieS1, 3), from 2 mm to 40 mm to be filmed with the same setup. Goosenecks from generic USB LED lamps were used for precise fine adjustment of lighting. The dim, visible LED of the gooseneck was replaced with a high power, narrow beam IR emitter (SFH 4550, Osram, Germany).

3.6 SPEED CONTROL

To reduce parameter dimensionality, I maintained constant speed for all experiments. However, to assess specialized behaviours such as potential hovering abilities in VR, I required the additional parameter of speed control when testing the hoverfly, *Eristalis tenax*. I provided speed control by making use of Wing Beat Amplitude Sum (WBAS) (Figure 3.9 on page 52, Equation 3.5). The new speed was based on linear transformation of WBAS and this required us to specify four parameters (Min flight speed, Max flight speed, Minimum of WBAS, Maximum of WBAS). This approximation ignores nonlinear effects. (Equation 3.6)

$$WBAS = LeftWingAmplitude + RightWingAmplitude \quad (3.5)$$

$$NewSpeed = \frac{(MaxSpeed - MinSpeed) \cdot (WBAS - minWBAS)}{MaxWBAS - MinWBAS} \quad (3.6)$$

3.7 VR INITIALIZATION

The VR has a virtual area spread across 1025 m x 1025 m. By precise tiling of the textures, the boundaries are setup to have periodic boundary conditions allowing an “infinite” world. Heading is defined as the angle with respect to North, which is aligned to the 6Y-axis. The insect had an initial virtual location at (513, 513, 1) and 0° heading unless stated otherwise. The product of WBAD

and gain was used to move the visual scenery and close the loop. The insect had its translational velocity set to 1 m/s. Once the insect was flying (beating its wings) in the VR, the run was manually initiated. The run was stopped either when the insect stopped flying or when the trajectories overlapped to a reasonable extent, typically after 10 runs. The trial was complete when the reset criterion is met; i.e. when the trial duration exceeded the maximum bout duration parameter, typically 30 s. When the reset event occurred, the individual was virtually teleported back to the same initial position in a new world. The sudden change in visual scenery made insects fling their legs and this resulted in wing tracking errors. To prevent these teleportation artefacts, after every reset, for 0.5 s the insect was in open loop with zero velocity. The next 0.5 s, the insect was in closed loop but still with zero velocity. This allowed the insect to fixate on its object of interest and prevented random initialization artefacts. Only then, the insect's translation velocity was set back to 1 m/s and this entire process repeated after the next reset event. Based on the assay and experiment configuration, there were multiple scene choices to be tested. For example, in the tree assay, there were four parallel worlds: no tree, tree on left, tree on right and trees on both sides. Identical in every aspect except for the presence and location of the tree. After every trial reset, the individual was transported to a random selection from one of the 4 worlds to the same start location and orientation, keeping the background and sky scenery identical across the worlds. After teleportation, VR initialization was performed as described before starting the next trial.

3.8 FINDING THE RIGHT GAIN

For animals moving in fluids such as air, the relationship between biomechanics and translation is nondeterministic due to the stochasticity and nature of fluid dynamics. Thus, due to practical considerations, prior VR studies with flying insects^{15,16,28,29} arbitrarily selected a particular gain of their choice. However, gain values set limits on the ability of the animal to turn, compensate,

Figure 3.12: Representative optomotor response to a sweep of impose velocities and directions.

and translate in response to stimuli¹⁸, which results in over or underrepresentation of the animal's intended direction in space.

I used the optomotor reflex paradigm to measure each fly's compensation to externally imposed yaw rotations. An external turn was imposed on the insect and the insect reflexively compensated for these turns. The turns were repeated clockwise and counterclockwise for a given angular velocity. The angular velocities of these turns were increased exponentially and repeated again in decreasing order. Translational movement was disabled and the insect was only allowed yaw compensation. This entire protocol was repeated on the same individual again with a different gain. Thus, each insect was tested for all achievable combinations of impose velocities and gain. Response was then calculated as the product of the WBAD and gain. Error is defined as the difference between external impose velocity and response of the insect.

To provide an objective method to measure gain for tethered flying insects in my arena, I measured the range of gain where stability (mean of response error, measured as impose – impose response) and manoeuvrability (SD of response error) of the insect's virtual heading to externally

imposed yaw rotations in my arena were comparable. Optimal closed loop gain was estimated by measuring the range of gain where stability and manoeuvrability of the insect's virtual heading to externally imposed yaw rotations were comparable such that if their ratios are close to one.

For *R. pomonella* (apple fly), this region was around $36 \text{ deg/deg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ (i.e., the world moved 36° for every degree of wingbeat amplitude difference over 1 s) (Figure 3.13 on page 58. For *A. aegypti* (yellow fever mosquito), this region was around $75 \text{ deg/deg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ (Figure 3.14 on page 59). For males of *P. laeta* (crane fly), it was around $40 \text{ deg/deg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ (Figure 3.14 on page 59). However, female crane flies showed little to no stabilization response (Figure 3.14 on page 59). Similarly, *Daphnis nerii* (oleander hawkmoth) also showed no stabilization response (Figure 3.14 on page 59). This is likely due to lower wingbeat frequencies of female crane flies (50 Hz for female vs. 80 Hz for male crane flies) and hawkmoths (36 Hz for both males and females).

Figure 3.13: Error is defined as the difference between external impose and response by the insect (here *R. pomonella*). Stability is defined as the mean of the error, and manoeuvrability is defined as the SD of the error; 95% CI is indicated as shaded regions around the lines.

3.9 INSECT REARING AND PREPARATION

Rhagoletis pomonella (apple fly) were collected and maintained as previously described¹³¹. Briefly, Adult hawthorn and apple race flies were reared from collections of larval-infested fruit sampled

Figure 3.14: Error is defined as the difference between external impose and response by the insect (here *A. aegypti*, *D. nerii*, *P. laeta*). Stability is defined as the mean of the error, and manoeuvrability is defined as the SD of the error; 95% CI is indicated as shaded regions around the lines.

at a field site USA using standard *Rhagoletis* husbandry methods and maintained on a 15 L: 9 D light cycle at 22-25 °C and 65% humidity. All experiments were performed on sexually mature (12+ days post eclosion) wild *Rhagoletis pomonella* of both races. The larvae were hand collected from multiple sites in the USA.

Aedes aegypti (Yellow fever mosquito) were obtained as adults from Subaharan Kesavan, NBAIR, Bengaluru, India. *Eristalis tenax* (Hoverfly) were obtained as pupae from Polyfly, Almería, Spain. *Daphnis nerii* (Oleander hawkmoth) larvae were wild-caught and reared in the greenhouse, NCBS, Bengaluru, India. Wild *Pseliophora laeta* (Crane fly) adults were caught and used for experiments.

Insects were maintained in a 23 °C chamber, 60-75% RH in a 14 L-10 D cycle. *R. pomonella* were fed on the artificial diet of sugar and yeast (56), *A. aegypti* on raisins, *E. tenax* on pollen, *D. nerii* on Nerium leaves and *P. laeta* on sugar water. *R. pomonella* aged between 12 to 20 days post eclosion, *A. aegypti* and *E. tenax* at least 4 days post eclosion were selected that exhibited flight activity in the cage with undamaged wings. Tethered experiments were performed from 1000 to 1800 hrs. at room temperature 22-25 °C. *D. nerii* were tested between 1900 and 0100. The insects were cooled in ice for 3 minutes (10 minutes for the hawkmoth) and placed on a cold metal block. A minuten pin glued to a syringe needle was used as the tether. To make identical tethers, a custom jig was built (Figure 2.6 on page 30). A tether coated with a tiny drop of cyanoacrylate glue (Fevikwik, Pidilite, India) was lowered and carefully positioned between the insect's head and thorax using a micromanipulator (Narishige, Japan). Using a beard hair, a tiny amount of glue was teased between the gap and allowed to dry for about a minute. The insects were allowed to recover for about 20 minutes in a tiny humidified tip box. A Styrofoam ball (2mm OD, generic) dipped in sugar solution was given to the insect to provide nutrition and prevent dehydration. Insects that flew on the tether for over 3 minutes were tested in the VR arena. Insects that did not fixate on any target were discarded. For the vision and wind assays, I used head-fixed insects, while I used head-free insects for odour assays as head-fixed insects did not consistently respond to odour. This suggests head movements might be

critical for odour tracking. Further experiments would elucidate how head movements and antennal positioning is integrated during the search process.

3.10 SOFTWARE

The front-end GUI of VR was built using Python and PyQtGraph. It can control all the parameters of the VR. Saving and restoring of different default configurations has been added for the experimenter's convenience. The live mode section provides real-time visualization of trajectories, headings, experimental state variables and live histograms of WBAD. The GUI can also be customized by the user. The backend of VR was built on top of ROS. The ROS node graph has four major nodes. The camera node preprocesses and publishes the live stream of the camera. The kinemfly analyses the live stream and publishes the wing beat angles. The VR node uses the WBAD from kinemfly, computes the trajectory and stimulus states and publishes the trajectory. The GUI node subscribes to the trajectory to provide real-time visualization. During recording, the trajectory node is subscribed and saved as a rosbag file. This allows for the entire experiment to be replayed, as it is, later for analysis. To adjust to large graphical and computational loads, I used a gaming PC. It has an i7 5690K CPU (Intel Corporation, USA) and an NVIDIA 980 TI (Nvidia Corporation, USA) GPU with 32 GB RAM running Ubuntu 14.04. The data analysis and statistics were performed on the same computer using custom Python scripts.

3.11 TRAJECTORY ANALYSIS

Trajectories were analyzed based on their orientation vectors. Displayed polar plots represent the spread and directionality of the orientation data. Violin plots represent the histogram of the orientation data from the entire trajectory. Depending on the assay, I used absolute heading (orientation with respect to north), angle with respect to the virtual object, or angle with respect to the wind.

This put the relevant “target” at 0° . I used a Rayleigh test to check for directionality in the data. For the motion parallax data, I measured the number of trajectories that reached the virtual object and performed a binomial test between the two choices. For the odour assay, I compared the duration of in-plume traversals of different conditions with respect to slip alone using a one-sided Mann–Whitney U test. Where appropriate, 95% CIs are reported. Each of these plots and analyses was performed with custom Python scripts making use of Pandas (<https://pandas.pydata.org/>), SciPy (<https://www.scipy.org/>), and Seaborn (<https://seaborn.pydata.org>) graphing pipelines.